

under waterlogging, possibly because of its intermediate plant height and ability to elongate with rising water.

IET3235, IET3257, IET5853, and

Pankaj gave the highest yields under waterlogged conditions. IET3235 and Pankaj were also the highest yielders under normal water conditions.

and Pho Kha. At harvest, Page Sampe Tuah had the most spikelets per panicle; ARC6000, the most spikelets per square meter; and Shoa-nan-tsan and ARC6000, the highest spikelet fertility.

The table, which gives the best donors from our tests, shows that many indicas are more cold tolerant than the japonicas.

The possibility of selecting early lines at Los Baños, Philippines, in the wet season, despite the high temperature, was tested by comparing the growth duration of the 219 entries in the 1978 IRCTN planted both at

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Highlights of the Korea-IRRI Collaborative Program on Rice Cold Tolerance

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A collaborative Korea-IRRI program on rice cold tolerance was initiated in late 1977. The first experiments were conducted in 1978 at Chuncheon Branch, Crop Experiment Station, Office of Rural Development. This report highlights some of the experiments.

A total of 750 entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) and early generation breeding lines from Korea, Indonesia, and IRRI were subjected to continuously flowing cold water, 17 to 27°C, from the tillering stage until maturity. Varieties responded widely in tolerance. The best entries for each agronomic character follow:

Well-exserted panicles: Somewake, Oirase, Bandalbyeo, Thankote Marsi, IR5867-50-3-2-2-1, IR9202-22-3-2.

Short growth duration: Matsumae, China 1039, K140-52-3, Fuji 269, K39-96-1-1-1-2.

Intermediate plant height: Firooz, HP46, Habiganj Boro II, IR2403-PLPB-7-2-1-3B, IR4097-P1P6-1B, IR4999-B-Jn2B, IR5086-P1P6-2B, IR5467-2-2-2, IR10212-12, Jaliya, MPR-1, Paro White, Thankote Marsi.

High spikelet fertility: IR9202-32-2-3, IR8460-7-2-1, IR5868-112-1-7-1-1, IR2403-P1pB-5-4-1B, IR9202-25-1-2, China 988 (HPU16), China 988-LS 13.

Good phenotypic acceptability at maturity: IR5867-50-3-2-2-2, IR7167-33-1-7-3, IR7167-33-2-3-3, IR7167-33-2-4-1, IR7167-33-2-4-3, IR7167-33-2-5-1, IR9202-22-3-2.

To identify extremely cold-tolerant parents for the breeding program, the best Korean and IRRI selections were subjected to 17°C water from

tillering to maturity.

Naengdo 13 had excellent panicle exsertion. Fuji 269 and ARC6240 had the shortest growth duration. The tallest at flowering were Silewah, Heugdae gu.

Days (no.) to flowering at IRRI

Varieties that were excellent in at least 3 plant characters desired in low-temperature areas. Korea-IRRI collaborative program, 1978.^a

Agronomic character	ARC 6000	Leng Kwang	Stejaree 45	01 Byeoo	Ggae Byeoo	Shoa-Ga-Dau	Shoa-Nan-Tsan	HR 33
Good phenotypic acceptability	x	x	x	x			x	
Excellent panicle exsertion	x	x		x				
Optimum culm length		x			x	x	x	x
Earliness (days)	111	119	114	126	125	127	113	138
Stable growth duration	x			x	x	x		x
Good tillering	x	x						
Long panicles						x	x	x
High spikelet no./panicle					x			
High spikelet no./m ²	x	x	x				x	
High spikelet fertility	x	x	x	x			x	

^a x = desired characteristic is present.

Los Baños and at Chuncheon (see figure).

Entries with long growth duration at Los Baños generally also had long growth duration at Chuncheon (see figure). But 12 entries had short growth duration at Los Baños and relatively long duration at Chuncheon, probably because they were photoperiod-sensitive and the days in

Chuncheon were long.

Preliminary selection for early maturity can be done at Los Baños and entries which flower in more than 70 days can be removed.

Indica varieties in the IRRI germplasm collection with growth duration of 94 days or less at Los Baños were evaluated

in Korea. Most of the 240 varieties tested had early growth duration but the long day lengths in Korea apparently delayed 8 photoperiod-sensitive varieties.

Hungarian 1 and Tinpakhia were the earliest, 20 days earlier than the short growth duration Josaengtongil at 21.2°C water temperature. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Fatty acid content of rice leaves affected by bronzing disease

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Iron toxicity or *bronzing* is a major physiological disease of rice in Sri Lanka's wet zone. Cytological changes in diseased leaves have shown that the accumulation of brown globules in chlorophyllous tissues is a characteristic associated with bronzing. The brown globules are weakly acidic.

This study showed that brown globules have an affinity to stains such as Sudan III, Sudan IV, and Nile Blue – an indication that the globules are fat or oil droplets. To further ascertain that the brown globules are oil, the fatty acid contents of diseased and of healthy leaves were quantitatively compared.

Plant materials of rice varieties BG34-8, BG11-11, IR2061-214-2-7-6-3, and H9 were analyzed. BG34-8 and H9 were grown in liquid culture; BG11-11 and IR2061-214-2-7-6-3 were obtained from the IRRI-Sri Lanka collaborative iron toxicity screening site at Padukka. To induce iron toxicity, ferrous sulfate was added to the culture medium. The varieties grown in the field were planted in replicates; disease incidence was observed only in some of the replicates. Leaf samples were collected from healthy and severely bronzed plants. Lipids extracted from the samples were processed and the methyl esters of fatty acids were analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography. All fatty acids were identified by retention times and peak enhancements

Total area of peaks obtained in leaves of healthy and diseased plants of four rice varieties. University of Sri Jayawardenapura, Sri Lanka, 1977.

Designation	Total area (mm ²) in	
	Healthy plants	Diseased plants
BG34-8	1457	2128
H9	2914	4022
BG11-11	1263	2097
IR2061-214-2-7-6-3	3432	4516

with standard solutions. Fatty acid contents were calculated directly by the peak-area method (see table).

The carbon number of the fatty acid that were identified ranged from 6 to 20 and the C-20 acid was found only in the diseased condition. A two-way analysis of variance revealed highly significant fatty acid contents in the leaves of diseased plants and highly significant variations of the fatty acid contents of different rice varieties. ■

Suspected ragged stunt disease in India

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Rice ragged stunt disease, first reported in the Philippines, was later found in various parts of Indonesia. The disease, which has been identified as caused by a virus, is transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Specimens showing the characteristic symptoms of the new disease were first seen at the Regional rice Research Station, Chiplima, in 1975 and later at the Central Rice Research Institute,

Cuttack. In 1976 and 1977, plants with similar symptoms were again seen, but the incidence was low. Transmission studies are being attempted, and varieties from the germplasm bank will be screened to identify resistant donors. ■

A new type of malformation in rice

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A new type of rice malformation was observed in the germplasm maintenance plots at CRRRI in 1978 kharif. Affected tillers produced bunches of leaves that appeared like a fan; the tillers remained in the vegetative stage (see photo). At later growth stages, the upper portions of the tillers swelled, giving a false impression of an enclosed panicle due to the merging of the upper internodes and consequent crowding of leaves, covered by the outer leaf sheaths. In a few cases, incompletely emerged panicles with discolored spikelets aborted. Because the affected tillers had more internodes (7–10), their height sometimes exceeded that of the unaffected tillers. In other cases, a large number of shorter affected tillers gave the plants a bushy appearance. The leaves and internodes of affected tillers were crinkled and often twisted. Nodal branching was frequent. But vigor was not reduced in the vegetative stage. The malformed tillers often dried about a month after the unaffected plants matured.

Examination of the incompletely emerged and discolored panicles showed